

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 8: Course Evaluation Post-Training Questionnaire

Page 1: Information and Consent Reaffirmation

We would like to learn more about **your experience with the OSPARK Bootcamp**. This questionnaire will ask you about your social media strategy; how you feel about conducting open science outreach activities; and for your opinions on the OSPARK Bootcamp training course.

As a reminder, we are defining outreach activities as **anything which reaches out to and/or engages the community around your initiative**. This includes (but is not limited to) making social media posts, sending newsletters, community building activities, hosting events, creating podcasts, writing which is aimed at sharing your initiative such as blogs or journal articles, vlogging, and collecting feedback from the community.

This project is designed in line with the British Psychological Society (2021) Code of Human Research Ethics. We expect that the decision to participate or not participate is within the professional remit of participants. All responses are anonymous. *<add information about ethics approval>* For more information, see the full participant information sheet *<add link>*. We recommend that you download this for future reference.

We anticipate that this survey will take most people 15 minutes to complete.

If you have questions or concerns, please contact the researcher:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator
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Please indicate your consent to taking part by checking the boxes below:

- I have read and agreed to the terms and conditions outlined in the participant information sheet.
- I consent to taking part in this study.

We will be linking responses to the questionnaires using unique identifiers. Please create your unique identifier using the following:

- Your favourite dessert. If you don't know what your favourite dessert is, please enter your favourite colour, book, movie, etc.

- Your month of birth as a number.
- The first two letters of your mother's first name.

Please put a hyphen (-) between each element of the identifier.

For example: someone whose favourite dessert is tiramisu, who was born in January, and whose mother is called Mary would enter tiramisu-01-ma.

Please enter your code below:

Page 2: Knowledge

The OSPARK-aligned answer is highlighted in light green.

Below is a series of 9 questions about outreach strategy. These questions will assess whether your approach aligns with OSPARK's course content. Remember that there is no "right" answer with social media strategy—every person and initiative needs a tailored approach.

Who might be in the target market for an open science initiative?

- Students
- Researchers in academia
- Researchers in industry, the public sector, or nonprofit organisations
- Research professionals and support staff, such as lab managers and librarians
- Research funders and philanthropists
- University administrators
- All of the above
- I'm not sure

Conference talks and networking sessions are a form of marketing for your open science initiative.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

Which communications channel should you use to advertise your open science initiative?

- The ones with the most overall users
- The ones frequently used by the people I want to reach

- The ones which are easily accessible through my job
- I'm not sure

What is the most effective strategy to grow your open science initiative's social media page?

- Occasionally commenting on and sharing other initiatives' work
- Spending 1 hour per day "liking" every post on the account's timeline
- Using 20+ hashtags in every post, on every platform
- I'm not sure

What is most important in a talk about your open science initiative?

- Providing clear information about the initiative
- Connecting emotionally with the audience
- Both are equally important
- I'm not sure

What is the main benefit of short vertical videos, such as TikToks or YouTube Shorts, over long-form videos?

- There is often better discoverability through wider algorithmic reach
- Viewers are more likely to look at your profile and other content
- It's easier to establish a connection with the audience
- I'm not sure

Marketing and communications are primarily about...

- Promoting your open science initiative
- Providing value to your audience
- I'm not sure

Interacting with similar or competing open science initiatives is harmful to your open science initiative's marketing and communications goals.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

What would normally be included in a marketing and communications strategy plan?

- Broad guidance about the goals, style, tone, and channels you will use
- Specific step-by-step instructions on how to create each social media post
- I'm not sure

This is an attention check. Please select "false" to show that you are paying attention.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

Page 3: Self-efficacy

Imagine you were asked to conduct outreach activities for the open science initiative(s) you are part of. How confident would you feel doing this?

1. Not at all confident
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
5. Very confident

Please think about conducting outreach activities for an open science initiative. When you think about these activities, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Note: Rated on a 5-point Likert scale: strongly disagree (1), slightly disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), slightly agree (4), strongly agree (5).

- I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself.
- When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.
- In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.
- I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.
- I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges.
- I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.
- Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.
- Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.
- This is an attention check. Please choose "slightly agree" to show that you are paying attention.

Page 4: Training feedback

Please give us some feedback about the OSPARK Bootcamp training. This section of the questionnaire is completely optional — you're welcome to skip any question.

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

Note: Rated on a 5-point Likert scale: strongly disagree (1), slightly disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), slightly agree (4), strongly agree (5).

- The material was appropriate for the target audience
- The course was engaging
- I would recommend this course to others
- I learned techniques and strategies that I intend to use in my work
- The course is helping me work openly
- The course is helping me encourage others to work openly

What did you like about the OSPARK Bootcamp? What do you want more of?

What can we do to improve the OSPARK Bootcamp?

How much time did you spend on the email course and workbook on average? Please do not include meetings in your estimate.

- <1 hour / week
- 1-2 hours / week
- 2-3 hours / week
- 3+ hours / week
- Other (please specify) -----

How did you hear about this course?

Anything else you'd like to share?

Page 5: Closing message

Thank you for completing this questionnaire.

If you have questions or concerns, please contact the researcher:

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